

Reference List for the Entry: Fälschung(-sverhalten) [faking behavior]

Author: Jessica Röhner

Date: June 17, 2025

This document contains the full reference list from the encyclopedia entry “Röhner, J., & Schütz, A. (2019). Fälschung (-sverhalten). In M. Wirtz (Hrsg.), *Dorsch – Lexikon der Psychologie* (19. überarb. Aufl., S. 584). Hogrefe.” The original text is not included for copyright reasons. The reference list is provided here separately to help researchers find the cited works more easily.

References

1. Röhner, J., Schröder-Abé, M. & Schütz, A. (2011). Exaggeration is harder than understatement, but practice makes perfect! Faking success in the IAT. *Experimental Psychology*, 58, 464-472. <https://doi.org/10.1027/1618-3169/a000114>
2. Ziegler, M., MacCann, C. & Roberts, R. D. (2012). Faking: Knowns, unknowns, and points of contention. *New perspectives on faking in personality assessment*. In M. Ziegler, C. MacCann, & R. D. Roberts (Eds.), *New perspectives on faking in personality assessment* (pp. 3-16). Oxford: University Press. 10.1093/acprof:oso/9780195387476.001.0001